

EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF KORAKALPOK THEATER

Khayitboeva Oltinoy Rashid kizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10002677>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the emergence and development of the theater, the artists who contributed to the development of the Karakalpak theater, and the stage works performed by them.

Keywords: theater, art, culture, humanity, history, thought, national theater, reform.

As our great enlightened grandfather Mahmudhoja Behbudi said, the theater is really a laboratory, a place of good education and enlightenment. It is well known to all of us that the role and importance of theater art in the life of a person and society, in raising the spiritual world and thinking of the people is incomparable. Theater, one of the most popular and influential art forms in the world, has been calling people to humanity and goodness for centuries, serving to cultivate noble qualities and beautiful feelings in their hearts, and to strengthen the principles of peace, friendship and harmony, high morality and justice in the life of society. It is worth noting that the art of theater, which has a glorious history of more than several centuries and creative schools, keeps its rich traditions and values, keeps pace with the times, and develops consistently.

In this place, the Karakalpak theater also traveled a glorious path and reached its present position. We considered it permissible to once again focus our attention on the development process of Karakalpak theater art, which has a unique creative history. After all, in our country, attention is paid to the development of this type of art that leads to spiritual perfection.

In this way, with the decision of the Karakalpakstan Regional Executive Committee (Karakalpakstan Oblastliq Atqariw Komitet) on April 11, 1926, the Karakalpak State Academic Musical Theater named after Berdak appeared.

According to the order of the Education Department of Karakalpakstan on May 3, 1926, Zarip Fatikhovich Kasimov was appointed the artistic director of the Karakalpak national theater troupe "Morning Light".

On November 8, 1926, the first curtain of the "Morning Light" troupe was solemnly opened with the premiere of Kasim Auezov's three-act musical drama "Tilak Yolida". Zarip Fatikhovich Kasimov acted as the director of the play, and he was both the stage director and the prop designer himself. The decorations needed for the performance were also made by hand, Z. Kasimov was closely assisted by the director of the petting zoo Tukhvatullins. In order to increase the impact of the performances on the audience, many folk tunes were used, and the music of these tunes was composed by Kasim Auezov himself. In the summer of 1927, under the leadership of Zarip Fatikhovich Qasimov, the "Tong Nuri" troupe performed for the first time. will be on a big tour in Irot districts for two and a half months. The performance, along with public performances, introduces the creative works of local amateur circles and gives them advice.

Abdiraman Oteпов, working as a worker (khatkeri) of the village council in Kungiroт, came to the Council school for three months in the fall of 1927. He became interested in the work of the "Tong Nuri" troupe and began to participate in the troupe. Since Zarip Fatikhovich Qasimov has returned to his main profession as a teacher, Abdiraman O'tepov will be appointed artistic director of the "Morning Light" troupe from September 15 this year.

At that time, there were 27 amateurs in the troupe team, among them playwright Zholmurza Aymurzaev, a famous representative of our national culture, poet and writer Aytbay Matyakubov, philologist Genjebay Ubaydullaev, Aytjan Bakhsi, Khojalepesov, artist of service to Uzbekistan Madrayim Matchanov, one of the local talented girls Jumagul. Seytova, Gurbangul Bekmuratova, Maryam Temirkhanova, Perdegul Satekeeva, and T. Ismetullaev, J. Pirnazarov, K. Allaniyazov, B. Seytov, O. Toremuratov. Later, Khalmurat Saparov, Kaljan Begimov, S. Turdigulova, O. Zinalieva joined the troupe. talented young people will come and join.

The role of theater art is incomparable in restoring our rich and centuries-old spiritual and cultural heritage, realizing our identity, instilling our centuries-old values into the minds of young people. he wants to find answers to the problems that torment him. The theater can leave an indelible mark on the viewer's heart by telling a story about history or modern life in one and a half to two hours. It is not for nothing that at the beginning of the century, the moderns put the theater art on a par with the school and the press, and considered the theater as a pulpit, a classroom, a center of enlightenment, and a place of etiquette. As a proof of our words, we can see the audience's interest in the theater during this period, and the fact that they came to watch the two-day performances without melting.

By the decision of the Council of People's Commissars of Karakalpakstan on December 15, 1930, the national theater troupe "Morning Light" was established as the "Karakalpak State National Theater". Abdiraman Otepov was appointed the director and artistic director of the theater. After receiving the position of the state theater, the troupe was completed by selecting talented young people from amateur groups in the districts. Among them were people's favorite actress Ayimkhan Kazimbetova (Shamurtaova), Tokhta Rakhmatova, Yoldash Sharipov, Zayit Zaripov, Anar Kurbanova, Isak Shadiev, Jiyen Masharipov and other theater artists. The artistic director of the "Dawn Light" troupe, Zarip Fatikhovich Qasimov, a teacher who served Uzbekistan, and Qasim Auezov, the state leader and dramatist, brought the troupe from amateur to the level of the state theater. Abdiraman Otepov was always a consultant in the organization of the troupe and the staging of performances. Seifulgabit Majitovs were the main fans of the Karakalpak National Theater.[1]

But it should be said that during this period there were some problems in the art of Karakalpak theater. Despite the fact that the Karakalpak theater had the status of a state theater from the amateur level, there was a need for skilled and mature personnel in its creative team. Actors, directors, composers, stage managers in the theater were talented people, and the skilled baker was truly dedicated to his profession. It was very important for the development of theater art to acquire their special knowledge and skills in this field. Now, the main goal of the theater is to prepare the local youth as leading personnel, to attract directors, godmen and other specialists from the neighboring republics, and to train talented young people.

In the spring of 1934, when the Bukhara theater came on tour, the director R. Fayziev and his wife, dancer and ballet master Kh. He staged Ghulam Zafari's musical drama "Kalima", and his wife Kh. Fayzieva set the choreography for the performance.[2]

On the initiative of the leaders of our republic, the Karakalpak studio of the theater art institute named after A. V. Lunacharsky was opened in Moscow this summer, and 33 young men and women are sent to it.

In order to establish and develop professional theater in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, preserve the rich cultural heritage and traditions of our people, and educate young talents, on November 21, 1934, the Council of People's Commissars of Karakalpakstan issued the Decree "On the Reconstruction and Strengthening of the Structure of the Karakalpak State National Theater" special decision was adopted. According to this decision, further development of theater art in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, strengthening the position of this art form in society and people's life, strengthening the material and technical base of theaters, providing suitable conditions for the theater creative team, especially helping young talents closely with other countries. A lot of work has been done in order to attract professional, highly qualified specialists working in the exchange of skills. In particular, Russian and Uzbek troupes were formed in the state theater. In 1935, an accomplished expert and experienced director G. Omarov and godman B. D. Kamenov were invited to our theater from Kazakhstan. After getting acquainted with the conditions of the theater, G. Omarov went to the districts together with the actor and director Yoldash Sharipov in order to attract talented young people to the theater and bring out their talents. Starts/Sapar Khojaniyazov, Tarbiya Jolimbetova, Suliw Allamuratova, Anar Kurbanova, Yahit Allamuratova, Perkhon Awezova, who worked for many years in their work, and others. contributed. In the middle of 1937, he returned to his country. [3] However, his companion B.D. Kamenov worked as the patron of the theater until the end of his life (he passed away in June 1957) and is considered an artist who made a significant contribution to the development of the art of painting in Karakalpakstan.

Karakalpak studio was opened in 1934 under the Institute of State Theater Art in Moscow in order to strengthen the team of the Karakalpak State Theater with educated and mature professional actors, to enrich the educational and spiritual impact of the performances presented to the audience, and to fundamentally enrich the level of artistry. 33 Karakalpak boys and girls will be admitted to the studio on a selective basis.

The fact that classes in all specialized subjects in the studio are conducted in Russian, the lack of Russian language skills of the young people admitted to the studio, and the lack of knowledge of the Karakalpak language, culture, traditions, and rich folklore of the master studio managers O.I. . In addition, we have to say goodbye to some students because they risked entering the studio in order to see Moscow without fully understanding the complexities of the acting field. As a result, by 1936, only 23 of the 33 selected young people continued their studies.

Therefore, one of the heads of the studio, V. B. Bibikov, came to Karakalpakstan in 1936 and selected P. Avezova, Y. Allamuratova, T. Jolimetova, G. Shamuratova, Y. Sharipov, S. Khojaniyazov, M. Matzhanov, J. Shamuratov and amateur groups from the theater youth. He takes 16 boys and girls to study.[4]

In September 1936, the creative team of the theater started work with only 22 people. With a small troupe, it was difficult to stage serious, energetic, well-rounded, comprehensive works. For this reason, in order to provide practical support to our theater, in the fall of this year, under the leadership of the well-known director Zuhur Qabulov 16 specialists will be sent from Tashkent to Karakalpakstan. Among the actors, R.Shokirov, I.Kasimov, P.Davlatova, L.Usmanova are accepted into the theater troupe, F.Kharratov, M.Isahojaev, N.Hamidov and I.Naimov are accepted into the orchestra. the artistic director of the theater, musician and

composer B. Tumayan was appointed as the music director, and A. Tairov as the chief ballet master.

During the years of study in Moscow, the experienced pedagogues of the institute, Professor O.I. Pizhova, V.B. Bibikov, B.A. Bronskaya, led the Karakalpak studio. During this period, the knowledge and experience gained from famous people such as world-famous theater figures I.M. Moskvina, B.I. Kalachov, L.M. Leonidov, M.M. Tarkhanov, dramatist Vs. Vishnevsky, ushkish V. Chkalov, Kazakh poet Jambil Jabaev became an unforgettable period in the life of young people from Karakalpakstan. As a result of the hard work of the heads of the studio, for the future development of the Karakalpak theater, taking into account the need for national dramaturgy and national directing, Toresh Allanazarov, Yoldash Sharipov, B.Aymanov, Yoldash Mamutov were appointed as directors; Dramaturgy by Jholmuraza Aymurzaev, Sapar Khojaniyazov, Pirlepes Tilegenov; M. Zarekeev, A. Kamalov went to theater studies clubs, they were given individual lessons and trainings in these areas, they were given the opportunity to participate in rehearsals of leading Moscow theaters. Toresh Allanazarov Molerdin' "Scape's trick", Yoldash Sharipov's "Poverty is not to blame" by A.N. Ostrovsky, Yoldash Mamutov and B. Aymanov Vs. Vishnevski's "The First Horse Army" were officially attached as assistant directors in the diploma work of the students.

28 young men and women who graduated from the studio returned to Karakalpakstan in July 1939 and continued their creative activities at the Mother Theater. At the beginning of October of these years, a number of teachers of the institute came to Tortkol from Moscow, and after a few days of preparation, on October 14-22, the students' diploma performances were shown to the public of the republic.

These days, the cultural life of Karakalpakstan has truly turned into a theater festival. Every day, the hall was full, leaders of republican organizations, educational institutions, and even spectators from distant villages of Tortkol and Shabbaz districts spent the night in black houses on horse-drawn carts and watched performances.[5]

In accordance with the decree of the Presidium of the Dzhokorgi Council of the Soviet Socialist Republic of Kazakhstan dated October 25, 1939, the head of the studio O.I.Pijova, teachers B.V.Bibikov, V.A.Bronsky and godman V.I.Romansky were awarded the "Honorary Label" of our Republic for their efforts in training skilled personnel for our national theater.

Starting from November of this year, the theater group Toresh Allanazarov Molerdin' "Scape's trick", Yoldash Sharipov's "Poorness is not a fault" by A.N. Ostrovsky, Yoldash Mamutov and B. Aymanov Vs. Vishnevsky's "The First Horse Army" have been performing for a month and a half. went to all districts, delivered his skills to the people, and was well received by the audience. It lit up the faces of his teachers, the people of Karakalpakstan, who sent him their trust, and the theater team. This tour served them to expand the knowledge they gained in the studio and the lessons they learned in the master classes.

It is safe to say that 1940 was a productive year for the theater team. At the request of the leaders of our republic, in the fall of 1941, 10 days of literature, art, and culture of Karakalpakstan were decided to be held in Tashkent, and preparatory work began in the second half of the year.), K. Yashin's "Gulsara", J. Aymurzaev's "Oz toyogi uziga" (directed by Y. Sharipov) were successful. In the 10-day repertoire held in Tashkent, "Alpomis" by N. Dawqaraev, "Koklen botir" by M. Daribaev, J. Aymurzaev, A. Shamuratov's dramas "Aral Girl" and a big concert program were planned. At that time, since there were no state concert

organizations in our republic, the task of providing cultural services to rural workers was entrusted to the collective farm theaters opened in Shabbaz, Qipshaq, Khojeli, Konigrat, Shimbay and Takhtakopir districts. Preparations for the 10-day event planned to be held in 1940 began. A commission was formed by the government and it was headed by Qutim Orazov. Talented young people were invited from amateurs and collective farm theaters, and the total number of participants 486 people were identified.[6]

This year's events will be canceled due to the outbreak of war against the old Union on June 22 of this year. Because of the war, theater, like all directions, changed its plans and its repertoire again. Two concert brigades were formed, which included well-known artists such as Abbaz poet Dabilov, Sadiq poet Nurimbetov, Qiyas Jiraw Khayratdinov, Japaq Baksi Shamuratov, Esjan Baksi Kospolatov. They raised the spirit of the people, performed concerts in front of the citizens going to the front and went from village to village. The plays "Alpomis" by N. Dawqaraev, "Kurban Umarov" by S. Abdullakh and Chusti, "Russian People" by K. Siminov, "Lieutenant Elmuratov" by J. Aymurzaev, "Oftobkhan" by K. Yashen, staged during the war years, show people loyalty to the Motherland, love for country, they were works that served to educate in the spirit of noble ideas such as national pride.

Despite the difficulties of this period, Usman Yusupov, the first leader of the republic, when he came to Karakalpakstan in the spring of 1943, saw the play "Alpamis" and expressed a warm opinion. Not long after, by a special decision of the government of Uzbekistan, it was transferred to the level of III-category drama theater, II-category state musical drama and comedy theater, and the state unit reached 250 people and a subsidy of 1.5 million soums was allocated. Acting in the theater, Choir, singing and ballet studios were opened, and a small symphony orchestra was formed.[7]

"Takhir-Zukhra" by S.Abdulla, "Tazagul" by R.Majitov, "Besh somliq kelin" by M.Ordubadi, "Don't be jealous" by S.Khojaniyazov, "Kizil Gul" by Alizade, "Kizil Gul" by Zholmurza Aymurzaev were performed on the stage of our theater. "Aygul-Abat", "On the banks of the Amudarya", "The Russian Question" by K. Siminov, "Golden Lake" by Uygun, "Kazi Korpesh-Bayan suluv", "Girl's Jeep", "America" by B. Lavrenev It should be noted that various thematic and genre plays like "Voice" were truly spiritual food for our people.

In 1946-1951, T. Allanazarov, who started his career as a professional director at the Karakalpak directorate, graduated with honors from the directing department of the Theater and Art Institute in Tashkent, and was appointed the chief director in 1940.

During the productive career of T. Allanazarov, Hamza's "The Rich Servant", A. Qahhar's "Aching Teeth", "Yangi yer", G. Mukhtarov's "Family Honor", I. Dyankonov's "Decorated Wedding", Moler's "Tartufe", "Stolen Happiness" by I. Franko, "Happiness" by S. Khojaniyazov, "Secrets of the Heart" by B. Rakhmanov, "White Flower" based on the novel "A Ghost Made by Iloy" by the Indian writer Shudraki saw the stage. we can witness that the plays are artistically high, aesthetically attractive, rich in directorial findings and, of course, the professional skills of the actors have increased significantly.

A. Abdaliev, A. Juzimbetov, A. Juginisov, A. Erimetov, B. Qurbanov, Sh. Otemuratov, Z. Piyazov, B. Tursinov, A. Khojanazarov, who graduated from the theater institute in Tashkent in 1955, joined the theater after the students. were educated mature professionals.

The 10 days of literature, art and culture of Karakalpakstan held in Tashkent from January 24 to February 2, 1957 became the main event in our cultural life. Nasimov, F.Nazarov, director

A.O.Ginzburg, theater director M.Musaev, ballet master E.A.Petrosova, choirmaster S.Davletkeldieva and other experts came to Nukus, gave advice and provided practical help. , "Garib Ashiq" by A. Begimov and T. Allanazarov, and "Raushan" by J. Aymurzaev were shown, and the mass media of the republic expressed warm opinions about the play. At the end of 10 days of Karakalpakstan literature, art and culture, actors Y. Sharipov, G. Sheraziyova, R. Seyitov, Y. Mamutov, composer A. Halimov "People's Artist of Uzbekistan", director T. Allanazarov, actors O. Dauletova, S. Karabaeva, M. Matzhanov, Z. Zaripov were awarded the title of "Artist of Meritorious Service to Uzbekistan" and several stage devotees of Karakalpakstan. In 1968, one of our leading actors, A. Shamuratova, was awarded the title of "People's Artist of the Union".The heads of the governments of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan paid enough attention to the training of skilled personnel in theater, art and culture, as well as in other areas, and since the 1960s, special Karakalpak groups have been accepted by the Tashkent Institute of Theater and Art and Culture every 3-4 years. and our talented young people of the Tashkent State Conservatory and the Yaqori School of Choreography were given the opportunity to get an education. R. Toreniyazov continued T. Allanazarov's directorial path after the 1960s, while Q. Abdireymov, N. Ansatbaev raised the art of directing to even higher heights. The names of B.D. Kamenov, K. Sayipov, I. Alibekov, make-up artist B. Sharipov, who worked for the theater for many years in decorating the scenery of each performance, are written in golden letters in the history of our theater. It is worth mentioning the effective work of B. G. Shafrannikov, J. Shamuratov, A. Halimov, A. Sultanov, Kh. Turdikhulov, A. Khayratdinov, S. Paluanov, N. Mukhammeddinov, K. Zaretdinov in musicalizing the performances of our theater.

K. Sultanov, E. Dauletov, A. Sapargaliev, G. Doshumov, S. Otepbergenov, K. Yusupov, O. Umitkulov, O. Dawletova, R. Adikova, T. Akhmetova, Y. Allamuratova, who achieved public acclaim with their acting skills. S. Awezova, Sh. Otemuratov, A. Juginisov, Z. Piyazov, D. Ranov, J. Bekmuratov, J. Palimbetov, M. Khalmuratova, Z. Sayipova, Kh. Saparova, M. Ismailova, B. Uzagbergenov, M. Sapayeva, J. Sagindikova, T. Qayipnazarova, O. Kasimbetov, B. Nazarimbetov, S. Ganiyeva, J. Sultabaev, Q. Qallandarov, B. Baymurzaev, young artists M. Usenov, S. Annaqulova and other stage devotees. is mentioned.

By the special order of the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 23, 2017, the Karakalpak State Academic Musical Theater named after Berdak was granted the status of the Karakalpak State Academic Musical Theater. , 102 musical dramas, 224 drama works were staged.

Among them, the first Karakalpak national opera "Ajiniyaz" by N. Mukhameddinov in 1987, the opera "Maysara's trick" by S. Yudakov in 1989, the opera "Aleko" by S. Rakhmanov in 1992, the second Karakalpak opera "Tumaris" by K. Zaretdinov in 2013, 2019 In 2020, N. Mukhammeddinov's opera "Gulayim" and in 2020 K. Zaretdinov's opera "For the People" enrich the theater repertoire. In 1996, the first Karakalpak national ballet was the ballet "Oyjamal" by N. Mukhammeddinov, in 2015 the second Karakalpak ballet was the ballet "Forty Maiden" by K. Zaretdinov, and now work has begun on another major work, preparations are underway for the ballet "Umri Zoya Star" by K. Zaretdinov . Among the works created on the basis of historical events and epics, in 1991 T. Allanazarov, A. Begimov's drama "Stranger Lover", in 1992 K. Matmuratov's drama "Sharyar", in 1996 A. Oripov's "Sahibqiron", in 1999 Berdak's musical "Treason to Justice" drama, musical drama "Alpamis"

by N.Dawkaraev in 2007, musical drama "Berdak" by K. Matmuratov in 2016, musical drama "Edige" by K. Rakhmanov in 2017, musical dramas "Garib Ashiq" by T. Allanazarov, A. Begimov in 2018 re-enacted. Currently, our theater is staging comedy and historical works along with folk-comedy, folklore-ethnographic performances based on the needs of the audience.

References:

1. Bayandiev, T. "History of the Karakalpak Theater". - T: UzDSMI, 2009 -P. 23.
2. Allanazarov, T. "The mold of the national director in the Karakalpak theater". - T: Knowledge, 1996 - P.43
3. Tursunov B. "The development of Karakalpak dramaturgy and theater
4. "Avdarma pesalardin effect". - Karakalpakstan, 1984, -P.52
5. Tursunbaev S.. Theater history. -T.: Tashkent, 2005. -P.14
6. Sharipova G. "Music and its teaching methodology". - T. "Turon-Ikbal" publishing house, 2011.- P.21.
7. Bekmatov S. The art of security. Instructional manual. Tashkent. 2007. - P. 14.
8. Boymirzaev H. "Methodology of learning music". - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1995. - P.52.